

were based on 10 plants/genotype.

Overall disease severities were considered to sum the effect of partial resistance components.

In the UBN, one row of each genotype was sown, with three replications. Disease severities were measured by using 0-9 scale (*Standard evaluation system for rice*).

The disease severities in the artificial inoculation test and the mobile nursery method indicated differences in partial resistance (see table). Because of high disease pressure in the UBN, fewer differences were found among the test genotypes.

The mobile nursery method could be used to identify levels of partial resistance to *P. oryzae* in advanced breeding lines.

Leaf BI severity differences in 3 methods of screening.^a Goiânia, Brazil.

Genotype	Inoculation with virulent race IB-1 (MDS) ^b	Mobile nursery (MDS)	Uniform blast nursery (av. score) ^c
Ferrinho	0.78 a	0.74 ab	8.3 a
Oitentão	0.71 a	0.85 a	6.0 d
Cam Roxa	0.67 a	0.57 bcd	6.0 d
Pedregulho	0.63 ab	0.61 abc	7.0 bc
Paga Divida	0.62 ab	0.71 ab	6.0 d
IAC 47	0.43 bc	0.43 cde	7.0 bc
IRAT104	0.39 c	0.12 f	6.0 d
Chatão	0.37 c	0.37 de	6.6 cd
Arroz de Guerra	0.33 c	0.31 ef	7.6 ab
IRAT13	0.31 c	0.36 de	7.3 bc

^aIn a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by Tukey test. ^bMean disease severity, av of 3 replications. 0 = highly resistant, 1 = highly susceptible. Severity values grouped into 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, and 1.0. Two types of susceptible lesions, type I and type II, were scored 0.25 and 1.0, respectively. Type I = restricted isolated susceptible lesion types with reddish brown margin, rarely coalesce. Type II = lesions with water soaked appearance, color ranging from white to grey, spindle shaped to irregular, rapidly coalesce. The infection coefficient multiplied with disease score for lesion type with severity values will give a maximum disease rating of 0.25 to lesion type I. ^c*Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale, av of 3 replications.

Insect resistance

Effect of rice gall midge (GM) resistance on parasitic behavior of *Platygaster oryzae* Cameron

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We studied the influence of GM resistance in rice on the parasitic activity of the GM parasite *Platygaster oryzae* Cameron during Oct 1987. Twenty rice accessions with different levels of GM resistance were raised in the field in 1-m rows, spaced 15 cm between hills and 20 cm between rows. GM incidence was recorded 30 and 50 d after transplanting. Parasitization was taken as the percentage of parasitized galls in each accession.

Five parasitized and five unemerged galls from each accession were collected and held in test tubes with water. Emerging adults were counted. Parasitization of rice GM ranged from 9.04 to 100%. The correlation between incidence of rice GM and its parasite

Correlation^a between GM and its parasite in rices with different resistance levels.

Accession	GM incidence (%)	Damage score	Parasitization (%)	Adults that emerged (no.)
RP1579-4-6-1	1.81	3	100.00	17
RP2362-110-40-1	3.63	3	50.00	26
IET9556	3.63	3	50.00	16
RP2432-105-7-1	3.63	3	66.66	25
IET9690	5.35	3	25.00	31
RP2199-41-25-34-55	5.55	5	40.00	30
IET9700	8.77	5	66.66	42
RP2199-3-3-1-1	9.09	5	40.00	42
RP2431-11-14-3	14.81	5	37.50	39
RP2311-276-71	14.81	5	50.00	42
TKM4	18.18	7	22.22	41
CO 27	27.27	7	40.00	46
CO 12	30.90	7	32.00	44
ASD9	38.18	7	45.76	43
TKM1	48.21	7	33.82	46
IR60	63.63	9	32.43	49
TNAU831520	81.48	9	9.04	45
CO 35	94.54	9	26.79	47
IR20	96.42	9	10.00	44
IR30	98.18	9	28.71	45

$$^a r = (-0.627)**; Y = 52.923 + (-0.377)X.$$

was negative. Resistant accession RP1579-4-6-1 had 1.81% GM incidence and 100% parasitization. TNAU831520 had 81.5% GM incidence and only 9.04% parasitization (see table). Adult parasites emerging from a single gall ranged from 16 to 47. In general, adult emergence was low from resistant rice accessions. □

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